

THE PECULIARITIES OF INTERNET-BASED MATERIALS IN TEACHING WRITING

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Abstract: The rapid development of the Internet in the 1990s has had a widespread impact on students' learning and knowledge acquisition in terms of foreign language learning. From this moment on, the Internet becomes an extraordinary source of information in the practice of teaching foreign languages. This article attempts to highlight the main advantages of using the Internet and modern computer technologies in the practice of teaching foreign languages.

Key terms: acquisition, internet-based materials, teaching writing.

Writing is one of productive skill which requires the writer to be able to generate ideas and support them with some supporting sentences with accurate and correct grammar. By using correct grammar, the writer can transfer his/her opinions, facts, and experiences well. However, in producing a coherent, fluent, and extended piece of writing is probably the most difficult thing to do in language. The steps done by the teacher in teaching using internet-based materials are: selecting a website, deciding the target of learning, topic, objective, arranging evaluation tool and giving score; the students can enhance their writing.

There is an opinion that the use of technology in teaching foreign languages is not new. Tape recorders, language labs and videos have been widely used in English language teaching since the 1960s. In the early 1980s, computer technologies and materials began to be used in the practice of teaching foreign languages; Soon these methods were classified as recommended and then mandatory methods of teaching foreign languages. In line with widespread access to information and communication technologies in the 1990s, the use of computer technology in foreign language teaching practice turned to the use of the Internet and network tools [1].

The rapid development of the Internet in the 1990s has had a widespread impact on students' learning and knowledge acquisition in terms of foreign language learning. From this moment on, the Internet becomes an extraordinary source of information in the practice of teaching foreign languages. This article attempts to highlight the main advantages of using the Internet and modern computer technologies in the practice of teaching foreign languages.

Teachers involved in the practice of teaching foreign languages can obtain any type of information on the Internet. The Internet also provides an answer to almost any question. Most teachers believe that they can get a lot of benefit from using online resources. The Internet is used as a way to obtain information, restore knowledge, or exchange experiences with other teachers from other countries. With the help of the Internet, advanced training for teachers, all kinds of testing and obtaining certificates are available, confirming the level of language proficiency and skill of the teacher. Warschauer, Shetzer and Meloni proposed five main reasons to use the Internet to teach a foreign language (English) [2]. The reasons are as follows:

- 1) authenticity;
- 2) literacy;
- 3) interaction;
- 4) living language factor;
- 5) empowerment.

Scientists believe that the Internet provides a low-cost method of learning a foreign language that meets the needs of 21st century learners [3]. The Internet provides the opportunity for students of a foreign language to interact with native speakers of the target language up to 24 hours a day, thereby introducing the student into a constant active process of learning a foreign language, and also allowing him to choose the time and place of study.

In addition, Warschauer and Whittaker identify several possible reasons for using the Internet in foreign language teaching [4]. One explanation is found in the claim that the linguistic nature of online communication is desirable for promoting language learning. Another possible reason for using the Internet in teaching foreign languages is that network resources create optimal conditions for teaching writing, as they provide a genuine audience for written communication. The third possible reason is that online communication greatly increases student motivation. The fourth possible reason is the confidence of Internet users that mastering computer skills is important for the future successful functioning of the student in the process of Internet communication. This does not imply the use of the Internet to learn a foreign language, but, on the contrary, the motivation to learn a foreign language for the subsequent good orientation of the student on the Internet.

So, both sides of the process of learning a foreign language - the teacher and the student - are interested in the use of Internet technologies in the process of learning a foreign language.

Benefits of using online resources for teachers

Mark Warschauer and Deborah Healy state that the Internet is one of the factors that has a significant contribution to promoting the use of computers for language learning [5]. The rise of computer-mediated communication via the Internet, more than anything else, changed the use of computers for foreign language learning for the learner in the late 20th century. With the advent of the Internet, the computer—both in society and in the classroom—has been transformed from a tool for information processing and display to a tool for information processing and communication. First-time language learners can now communicate inexpensively and quickly with other learners or native speakers around the world.

In addition, Dudeney [6] also mentions one of the advantages of using computers and the Internet in the practice of teaching and learning languages, especially for teachers. He mentions that, essentially, the computer and live language communication have now become a shared resource, always available to the target audience on the board [7]. Teachers and students can use the board to display CD-ROM and Internet content, and this content can be annotated, illustrated, saved and printed. In most situations, this content can be used as a special resource.

The next advantage of using the Internet as a means of teaching a foreign language is the opportunity for the teacher to improve their own knowledge, skills and abilities in a foreign language [8].

Below are some professional journals and journals that are presented with an online version on the Internet.

1. TESL-EJ - focuses on the theory and practice of language teaching.
2. Online TESL Journal, which includes short, practical articles.
3. Language, Learner & Technology - a research journal for second language teachers.
4. CALL-EJ online - covers machine language.
5. Kairos - magazine about computer writing.

Teachers can also join international organizations to maintain close professional contacts with colleagues from other countries, keep abreast of new

educational technologies, and improve their teaching methods. Warschauer, Schetzer and Meloni [9] identify some international professional organizations that have their own websites. Below is a list of these organizations.

1. TESOL
2. International Association of Teachers of English as a Foreign Language
3. Japan Association for Language Teaching
4. Association of International Educators
5. National Council of Teachers of English
6. American Association of Applied Linguistics
7. Linguistic Society of America

Finally, through the Internet, teachers can obtain information related to the publication of materials on teaching foreign languages. Many publishers, such as Longman or Oxford University Press, often publish catalogs of their publications on their websites [10].

Considering the important role of the Internet in the modern life of every individual, the use of the Internet in the practice of teaching foreign languages is inevitable. In general, the use of Internet resources in the context of teaching foreign languages provides benefits for both teachers and students. The use of innovative technologies, such as the Internet and network resources, is also a motivator for the intellectual development of students in the educational aspect.

List of references:

1. Акай О.М., Завгородняя Г.С., Царевская И.В. РОЛЬ ИНТЕРНЕТ-ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ КОНЦЕПЦИИ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ // *Современные проблемы науки и образования*. – 2015. – № 5. URL: <https://science-education.ru/ru/article/view?id=21913>
2. Хошимхуджаева, М. М. (2013). Мотивационно-номинативные свойства фитонимических лексем в английском, русском и узбекском языках. В мире науки и искусства: вопросы филологии, искусствоведения и культурологии, (1 (24)), 114-118.
3. Хошимхуджаева, М. М. (2017). Мотивологический анализ английских, русских и узбекских фитонимов с компонентом-антропонимом. *Проблемы истории, филологии, культуры*, (1 (55)), 369-378.

4. Turaeva, U. (2021). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH LEGAL TERMS LEGAL LINGUISTICS: HISTORICAL FOUNDATIONS, BASIC CONCEPTS AND ASPECTS. *Berlin Studies Transnational Journal of Science and Humanities*, 1(1.6 Philological sciences).

5. UMIDA, T. Characteristics, Methods and Challenges of Translating Law Terminology. *JournalNX*, 6(11), 312-316.

6. To'rayeva, U. (2023). THE ORETICAL AND PRACTICAL BASIS OF TRANSLATION OF TERMS. *Scientific Journal of the Fergana State University*, 29(4), 64. Retrieved from <https://journal.fdu.uz/index.php/sjfsu/article/view/2758>

7. Абдиназаров, У. (2023). INGLIZ VA O 'ZBEK TILLARIDA GIPPOLOGIK TERMINLARNING LINGVISTIK TADQIQI. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(9).

8. Qushoqovich, A. O. K. (2022). O 'ZBEK TILIDA YILQICHILIKKA OID TERMINLARNING O'RGANILISHI. *Journal of new century innovations*, 18(1), 37-40.

9. Djabbarova, S. (2023). NON-EQUIVALENT LEXICON IN THE MIRROR OF NATIONAL CULTURE. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 3(6), 986-988.

10. Turakulova, P., & Turaeva, U. (2023). THE MAIN METHODS OF WRITING COMPLAINT LETTER. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11 Part 2), 112-114.

11. Khurramova, D., & Turaeva, U. (2023). THE ART OF LETTER WRITING. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11 Part 2), 11-13.

